

European ECOsystem for green Electronics

Experts' analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT) related to Circular Economy strategies for WEEE reduction

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1. Introduction

1.1 The EECONE project ecosystem

The objective of the EECONE project is to foster the creation of a European ecosystem for green electronics with the ambition to reduce e-waste on a European scale. To this end, 48 entities from 16 European countries covering different sectors of activity have joined forces to propose practical ways of reducing the volume of e-waste in the EU. Crucially, the entities that make up EECONE represent all parts of the value chain. EECONE's approach is interdisciplinary, covering the social, economic, technological, and policy aspects.

EECONE's vision is to develop and embed the constraints linked to managing the end-of-life of electronic products from the very beginning - in the development or process design. EECONE is paving the way as a first step toward a zero-waste electronic industry. The "6R concepts", namely, Reduce, Reliability, Repair, Reuse, Refurbish, and Recycle, fully guide EECONE.

1.2 Objective of the document

This document leverages the EECONE ecosystem partnership to deliver an anonymised SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) relative to the project's objectives, i.e. the application of 6R circularity approaches for WEEE reduction. This document delivers key insights, most of the time in the form of direct quotes, directly from experts from the EECONE ecosystem. Hearing directly from the experts is the best way to get a feel for how the people making up the European electronics industry are working, and struggling, on a daily basis towards the complex goal of WEEE reduction.

1.3 Methodology

Interview candidates were selected on the basis of their answers to a preliminary "Ecosystem Understanding Survey" launched in July 2024 on the EECONE website and closed in October 2024¹. From the 74 survey respondents, interview candidates were selected first for their high level of expertise and years of experience in one or several of the 6Rs, as indicated in the survey. Candidate selection also considered respondents' companies position in the electronic market, size and status (public/private), aiming to cover a range of companies as diverse as possible. In total 16 respondents were contacted and 10 agreed to be interviewed.

A common interview questionnaire was prepared to support in the gathering of consistent information on how each organisation is experimenting the circularity transition. 10 interviews were carried out between April and June 2025 to understand companies current strategies regarding the 6Rs, the challenges they face, the opportunities and threats such challenges bring, as well as their strength and weaknesses to overcome them.

All interviews were structured to last approximately 1 hour. Most interviews were carried out online by one interviewer, either from CEA or STM. Interviews were transcribed using: notes taken during interviews, interview recordings, and automated transcriptions.

¹ The survey results were published at the SUSTAIN-E Summer School on sustainable Electronics, Grenoble, France, <https://www.eecone.com/eecone/home/>

1.4 Study participants

As mentioned above, participants were carefully selected to offer a wide diversity of organisations. Participants from SME (private), large companies (private) and research organisations (public) were selected [Figure 1][Figure 2]. Organisations were also selected to cover most of the electronic value chain [Figure 3]. All interviewees had a scientific background (engineer/chemist) [Table 1], but diverse positions in their company [Table 2].

Figure 1: Type of organizations covered in the interviews

Figure 2: Organization sectors covered by the interviews

Figure 3: Organization position in the electronic value chain

Table 1: Participants’ background

Background	
Engineer	9
Chemist	1

Table 2: Participants’ position

Position in the organization	
R&D	5
Quality with reliability and surface mount expertise	1
Sustainability manager	1
Sales	1
CEO	2

1.5 Structure of this document

This document is structured into four sections focusing on the different aspects of the analysis: The document starts with **Strengths**, focusing on companies’ current capabilities. Next we discuss **Weaknesses** currently being addressed by partners and **Threats** which endanger the ecosystem’s efforts. We finish with the more optimistic **Opportunities** section. [Figure 4] below represents a brief summary.

Figure 4: SWOT analysis summary

The conclusion presents the most powerful elements participants shared during the interviews, especially regarding the best **Course of Action** towards increased circularity and sustainability. We also conclude with remarks about the **Role of Data** in promoting the transition to 6R approaches for electronics ecosystems.

2. Strengths

To encourage 6R adoption, the EECONE partners already rely on a set of strengths which include their existing 6R expertise and business models, already deployed tools and methodologies and the strategic vision that has been developed by their respective organizations.

2.1 Building on existing 6R practices

In this section, we review a number of 6R strategies already being implemented by EECONE partners in their existing business activities:

Reduce

WEEE reduction strategies include optimizing material use, including work on compact PCBs and smaller Bill of Materials (BoM). The reduction of environmental impacts is further pursued through energy-efficient designs and by eco-design options:

“IoT often use batteries which often represent a higher percentage of the total environmental impact. We are working with a company in Sweden that has developed a bio-based photovoltaic cell based on a roll-to-roll process similar to printed electronics. Using that and a capacitor, you can replace the need for AAA batteries.”

“We offer our customers recycled plastics for the housing of our products.”

Reliability

Design expertise is leveraged to design highly efficient and durable semiconductor and electronic products. This includes e.g. dynamic voltage regulation approaches to minimize degradation and extend lifespan. Partners also build on their existing expertise to push further, e.g. in the field of component-to-PCB assembly reliability:

“It is possible to make component-to-PCB solder joints more reliable through different board designs and processes. For example, solder-mask defined pads are less reliable. More layers on the PCB reduce the reliability of the solder joint because the PCB gets stiffer. We talk with our clients and try to convince them to use more reliable options. Clients who need to push reliability even further are advised to use special techniques such as underfill (by filling the intermediate area where there is no solder joint, you get a stress relief) or corner bonds (use of high viscose material that stays at the edge of the component, where the stress is largest).”

Repair

More surprisingly, repair is already a key concern and business activity for certain EECONE partners:

“Repairability is the heart of our business. We develop testing methods for critical electronic equipment that must function for decades. Repair and maintenance are also essential in this field. For example, a nuclear power plant can have up to 15000 different PCBs that are required to last until the end of the plant’s lifetime. So our role is to source the components and reverse engineer the schematics. We then regenerate the PCB layers fabrication data to build a clone and a repair stock. For

programmable components, we perform aspiration of non-volatile memories to reflash components.”

“We also provide advice to customers on repairability at the system level. Post production PCB repairability requests come from customers whose aim is not to reduce waste but as a cost savings measure. Repairability lowers typical yield loss of 2% in production lines to 1% which saves money. Repair is facilitated by putting more distance between components. BGA packages also facilitate resoldering of changed components.”

“In aerospace applications, it is very common that components are kept 10 years in stock. Components older than 3 years are still under warranty but BGAs must be re-balled to avoid oxidation, implying that tin must be stripped to apply a new tin surface. This is needed to enable requalification of the products.”

“For repair, we don't use any glue or minimal size screws in our products (remote controls and IoT devices). So all our products can be disassembled by hand, without any tools.”

Reuse

To support EU objectives, some processes are being abandoned, e.g. cryogenic disassembly of batteries for recycling which prevents their reuse.

Refurbish

Refurbishing seems to carry a lot of potential:

“We provide 400,000 parts for refurbishment to our client². They do the disassembly and refurbishment. In practice, they keep the PCB and they replace the housing. You have to replace the rubber and plastic because it's scratched, for cosmetics reasons, but you keep the PCB which carries most of the environmental impact because you have the integrated circuits on there.”

“We also try to offer refurbishment for our products, because it is actually cheaper than buying a new one if you send them back, but we haven't had any request for it.”

Recycle

EECONE partners are active in the promotion of material recycling and recovery, especially for e-waste and in the exploration of novel robotized approaches, e.g. for the disassembly of battery designs. For recyclers, the reuse of the materials that are recovered in the recycling processes is constantly in mind. To this end, collaborations are key.

2.2 Capitalizing on tools and methodologies in support of 6R

Environmental assessment is widely used by organisations to support their sustainability strategies. Usually, such assessments are done through Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). For example, a system manufacturer explained: *“For our products, we have made a LCA that has*

² a large mobile and internet equipment and service provider

been externally certified to the ISO 14 040 standards. We use this as a reference since all our products are similar". Another system manufacturer chose simplified LCA combined with Techno-Economic Assessment (TEA) to "guide design decisions", and "help embed sustainability in early design stages".

Environmental assessment is used by both private and public organisations. For instance, a system manufacturer explained that *"currently product carbon footprints are calculated on 80% of our products as this is a common client demand"*. Likewise, another manufacturer declared, *"one ISO 14040 LCA is adapted to the different designs, covering all the different product designed"*. Research and universities are also fully committing to LCA:

"Over the last 5-6 years, we have learned a lot about LCA. In terms of internal organisation, we have a shared workspace where we can share information, engage in discussions. [...] At University level, they are considering setting up training and courses (LCA, sustainability) for both researchers and students".

Nevertheless, environmental assessment in itself is not a sustainability or a 6R strategy, it is rather used as support, an enabler of such strategies. For example, to a system manufacturer, LCA is the foundation of their *"Environmental Management System"*:

"We try and integrate the LCA into the design stage, we are not just doing the LCA at the end. In two days, we can identify the hotspots, and then explore the benefit of different design alternatives".

In addition to supporting design decisions, LCA could be used as a way to determine the best circularity strategies. As explained by a recycler:

"different Rs are often addressed separately and sometimes even in opposition to each other. A comprehensive approach that evaluates all six Rs together to determine the most suitable strategy for a specific product and sector is rarely implemented".

A system manufacturer explained how LCA could help making such choices:

"If you make something that has such a small impact that it doesn't actually matter what is its end of life, [...] you can incinerate it [...]. Yes, it doesn't sound as nice as having this complete recycling, but again, that is why I like to look at the LCA results, because to me, what actually matters is the environmental impact. Yes, it is not a beautiful closed loop, but maybe it is 90% better than what we are doing now. [...] That is what is interesting about the LCA".

Considering how widely used and powerful LCAs are, researchers are developing new methodologies for more precise and meaningful analyses. For instance, a laboratory

"identified 15 different methods to manage upscaling for LCA³, considering factors such as the maturity level of technology brought to market [...] the infrastructure and network needed to integrate new products into society, considering their potential for repair, reuse, and upgrading".

³ In the LCA context, Upscaling refers to extrapolating results from a small-scale system to a larger, real-world scale, e.g. upscale LCA results obtained in a R&D setting to an industrial setting

“These different LCA models help to reflect on how a company’s environmental impact changes as production quantities increase, and as the product is used by diverse users in society”.

The same laboratory also studies Absolute LCA, a methodology that considers planetary boundaries which

“sets limits on what we can consume, moving beyond traditional LCA that estimates potential environmental impacts based on past data, which may not accurately predict future outcomes. Absolute environmental assessment involves establishing shared principles for allocating environmental impact fairly across society, considering equity and needs”.

Beyond LCA, other organisations mentioned developing “digital-twins to reduce physical prototyping”, specific design frameworks to foster circularity such as “design-for-recyclability” and “cross-functional collaboration”.

2.3 Exploiting a strategic vision for 6R

A strong strategic vision is important to advance towards 6R. Often-cited strategies include:

- Leveraging pre-existing expertise, strong R&D capabilities and an innovation-driven culture. This often includes early integration of TEA-LCA⁴ with constant efforts for refining this knowledge:

“Main strategies leverage on strong expertise in high-efficiency semiconductor design and patented energy-saving technologies, supported by robust R&D and early integration of TEA-LCA for transparent environmental assessment.”

“Despite growing proficiency with LCA tools and databases, methodological constraints in LCA data also persist, requiring ongoing refinement. Overall, the approach balances innovation with scientific rigor and sustainability.”

“Our strengths include technical and organizational expertise, and our resources, in the form of in-house workshops, which enable in-depth root cause analysis. This gives us the ability to handle high volumes. We also offer secure storage in temperature-controlled rooms.”

- Exploiting established partnerships and supply-chains:

“We rely on established supply chains and secure storage to enable high-volume production and operational efficiency.”

- Investing in transparency and scientifically rigorous approaches:

“At some point, we’ll be publishing our results in an LCA paper, hopefully. So we have this transparency that we’re not just greenwashing.”

“We are beginning to gain a very good understanding of the various tools, databases and limitations for LCA.”

⁴ Techno-Economic Assessment associated to Life-Cycle Assessment

3. Weaknesses

3.1 Limitations of the current 6R strategy

While vision and strategy are fundamental for moving in more sustainable directions, sometimes, this is not enough:

“Our company did not reach its -25% CO2 reduction objective and we are currently analysing why and trying to identify better opportunities.”

EECONE partners struggle with a number of systemic challenges which currently limit the expansion of 6R strategies. Beyond the obvious financial aspects:

“Limitation is finding buyers willing to pay the extra price for more sustainable products, I call it the adoption premium.”

“We can offer green products, but if the customers don't want to buy them, then we're limited to sell them.”

EECONE partners mention difficulties such as dependence on supply chain partners for (upstream) availability and readiness of lower-BOM⁵, recyclable parts and (downstream) material recovery. Scaling of solutions for mass-markets is also a major current limitation. Systemic challenges extend to social aspects:

“Still, for me, there are some things we miss with LCA, like the social side. like, what's the social impact of moving from China manufacturing to Tunisia?”

Strategic change is therefore often limited by dependence on goodwill of co-workers:

“For the moment, I can only give advice to colleagues on repair/reworkability and try to gently steer them in this direction. This why regulation is good.”

Even the best of intentions can sometimes back-fire:

“We have the strategy of trying to solve the recycling of some kind of material, for example, batteries and PCBs, that's it, we don't even study the LCA. Of course, when we are in biggest projects, LCA and sometimes economic benefits are studied, but in our individual research, we don't look at it. So we go for the best product that we can achieve from this material, and we are very focused on recovery of the critical metals. Regarding LCA, in general when it is done the result for our processes are bad (compared to prime materials). This is because, sometimes we can save some CO2, but can also be using chemicals that are not very environment friendly. When you look into the economics this is very bad as well, because we are working at laboratory, so it is hard to compare our processes to already industrialised processes or a massive mine that is supplying the entire world. Furthermore, in the lab we are using electricity, but maybe in the industry they are using natural gas or solar energy. This is also true for our poor LCA results.”

⁵ Bill of materials

3.2 Technical barriers to improve the 6R strategy

Technical barriers could potentially be solved by investing in more R&D. Many interviewees highlighted the difficulty to “*Balance performance, cost and sustainability goals*”.

For instance, a system manufacturer highlighted the difficulties in complying with the “*need for miniaturisation while maintaining robustness*”. A recycler also explained the difficulties brought by miniaturisation at the end-of-life of electronics:

“One major limitation is that products are becoming smaller and thinner, with decreasing concentrations of valuable metals. For example, extracting gallium from electronic waste is particularly difficult and costly”.

Recycling is still possible but requires many more steps and might not always be profitable as recycled material would be too expensive.

A researcher on recycling also emphasised this issue focusing more on purity aspects:

“We are always talking about a Circular Economy and it's not really circular, because you cannot get the purity to reuse it in the same product, you need to change the industry in the majority of the cases. For example, the recycled copper that you get from PCBs, you will never use it in a PCB again. You can purify it to get 99,99% purity, but 3-4 processes are required. Of course, the price of copper is very high at the moment, so you can afford it, but if the price were lower it might not be the case. It is a balance between the economics and purity. For metals such as cobalt, platinum, gold and this kind of precious metal you can afford it because they are so expensive, but you will never use it for iron for example, because you're not getting paid for iron. This is something that you need to think of before the design of the product”.

A system manufacturer faced the same issue of compromising between circularity and cost:

“Investing in redesign and solutions to make products easier to disassemble is often more expensive and often this adds cost to the BoM (bill of material)”.

Besides the cost, increased disassembly also leads to increased security risks:

“Disassembly poses cybersecurity issues. We have had very recently internal discussions on reparability/cybersecurity compromises, and what might be possible”.

A researcher highlighted another issue: the compromise between circularity and the reliability of second-hand components:

“There are several barriers to implementing strategies for reusing and remanufacturing electronic components, such as concerns about the reliability of second-hand products and the challenge of monitoring component health over time, considering repairs and varying usage conditions. Overcoming these issues requires new sensors and data management systems, as well as addressing data ownership and sharing concerns”.

Finally, EECONE partners also pointed out the lack of “*standardised tools to evaluate a product's circularity*” as hindering their circularity strategies.

3.3 Non-technical barriers to improve the 6R strategy

Sustainable electronics brings challenges, especially regarding the time required for collecting reliable data and managing complex supply chains. Getting accurate information from suppliers, especially those further upstream in the supply chain, is difficult. As one expert explained,

“The supply chain for electronics is super complex and we’re a small company, so I can’t go to big resistor manufacturers and just ask for data [...] It has taken me years to get good data on integrated circuits.”

showing how proprietary information and limited transparency make it hard for smaller companies to fully understand environmental impacts. This lack of data affects the accuracy of Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) and makes refurbishment harder, since documentation is often missing and reverse engineering is needed.

Another challenge is the limited training available on Circular Economy principles and the use of techno-economic analysis (TEA) and environmental assessment tools. Designers often focus on cost and performance first, with sustainability considered only later. Introducing new, eco-friendly materials is also slow and costly due to long qualification processes.

Manufacturers face difficulties supporting product reuse and repair because there are no standard repair methods and failure data is often confidential. As noted,

“Repair strategies needs to become standardised. The minimum is to know what happens with certain component families.”

and efforts are underway in international committees and automotive groups to create standards on moisture sensitivity and soldering quality. These standards are important to ensure reused parts remain reliable and safe.

Beyond technical issues, sustainability also involves social and organisational challenges. Successful environmental assessments like LCA require good communication and cooperation between all stakeholders, including suppliers, manufacturers, and customers. Without this collaboration, sustainability efforts risk being disconnected from real-world practices.

In conclusion, improving sustainable electronics requires better data sharing, standard repair protocols, more training, and stronger industry collaboration.

4. Threats

Moving-away from linear, business-as-usual business models is a complex undertaking, requiring companies to juggle with product segment peculiarities,

“The margins in our product segment are so small that you don't have much room, and the customer doesn't have much interest, in paying 50% more for Flex PCB. It's been more useful within the IOT market.”

contradictory demands from clients,

“Clients currently have a contradictory request: more reparable and lower cost. Investing in redesigns and solutions to make products easier to disassemble is often more expensive and often this adds cost to the BOM (bill of material). These additional costs means that circularity is rejected both internally and by our clients. Clients need to see precise figures to validate the business case on the long term.”

4.1 Market and ecosystem threats to the implementation of 6R strategies

While profitability, competitiveness and lack of customer incentive to purchase more sustainable and circular products remain the main threats, ecosystem threats emanate from sector structuring and complex supply and reverse supply chains.

Upstream, raw material costs remain low thus complicating the economic viability of recycled materials.

Midstream, motivated actors face supply chain inertia, e.g. with tier suppliers reluctant to redesign legacy systems.

Downstream, reverse supply chains pose specific issues, such as the storage of components, e.g. old cards to reuse them for repairs) or the return of repaired cards to the circuit. New ecosystem actors become necessary:

“We use broker certifiers who certify that pre-used components have been tested.”

End of life poses its own challenges due to the need to manage e-waste across diverse geographical regions and the fragmentation of recycling regulations across EU. More importantly, the lack of ecosystem coordination between product design and end of life management processes poses threats to recyclers which require constant R&D and adaptation:

“The chemistry of batteries is evolving a lot. We started with NMC, that is nickel manganese cobalt, and now as the cobalt price rises, they are reducing the cobalt, and are using LFP which is not worth recycling as main components are iron and phosphorus (only between 1-4% Lithium). Now sodium batteries and aluminium batteries are also reaching the market.”

leading to an understandable cry-out from recyclers:

“Recycling will not solve any problem. So you need also to change the composition of the new products to get really sustainable. When designing new product, I mean, stop changing technologies so fast, or at least indicate how products are assembled, their composition. For now, for batteries, you need to open the cells: the battery, the

module, the cell to know whether this is a NMC or LFP. This is what is being worked on in the Battery Passport. This is a QR code providing a link to information such as the composition, battery geometry, and assembly information (glue, etc.) It is very difficult to disassemble these kinds of products if you don't know how to do it. Sometimes you don't even have the tools to open it because there are special tools for this kind of battery. This needs to change because you cannot recycle anything without this condition.”

Circularity, while a solution, can sometimes also become a threat choosing between different Rs is sometimes not obvious:

“For flex PCB, you're basically printing on PET and there's so little actual metal on there, you can put that directly into the PET recycling infrastructure and recycle it as plastic. From an LCA point of view, this is better than trying to recycling the metal. Also, sometimes it might actually be better to use traditional PCB because it lasts forever.”

Finally, the electronics **ecosystem** as a whole is responsible for insufficient global standardization efforts on circularity metrics and harmonized LCA methodologies.

4.2 Behavioural threats to the implementation of 6R strategies

The effort needed to change consumer mindset and willingness are daunting:

“Our customers are not interested. We're offering refurbishing as a service, but they don't use it. Because the products are still somewhat working, I guess, or consumers would rather buy a new one. Because refurbishing is new, it's a bit unknown. I think some of the customers aren't comfortable with the perceived risk. Or the cost difference with new products isn't that much”.

Consumers continue preferring new products novelty and shy away from effort and perceived risk:

“Currently, consumers aren't used to the thought of the extra effort that has to go into refurbishment or repair. You can design a product to be refurbished or to be repaired, but if that behaviour is not already in place in society, this is a big friction we have in society.”

4.3 Technological threats that may hinder the move to 6R

While past and ongoing technological developments naturally create barriers to 6R,

“We have a bit of a chicken and egg problem in sustainable electronics: you're competing with heavily industrialized processes where there's been decades of research and improvement into making the most efficient normal PCB. And it's an incredibly industrialized and efficient process. So starting something new, that hasn't been scaled up yet, is super hard to sell because the cost is higher and it's not a proven product. So there's the challenge of closing this gap to be able to sell enough and produce enough to generate economies of scale”.

“The continuous development of network technologies, whether in terms of Wi-Fi, protocols or fibre equipment, with a view to increasing data rates, obviously does not fit in with the reuse and reduce approach and runs counter to a repair strategy.”

as time passes, technological developments create new barriers to circularity:

“I feel that recyclability is getting worse because of the increase mixing of a lot of components that maybe improve usability, yield or whatever additional features you want. In most cases that translates into a use of a mixture of different materials that are very difficult to separate afterwards when you recycle it. PCB is a clear example of that: maybe there are 50-60 compounds inside one PCB, and there are a lot of different kinds of PCBs. This means that you need to design maybe 15-20 recycling processes depending on the composition of the initial PCB. It is very difficult to get an environmental and economical viable process when you don't know what is going into your process in the first place.”

“25 years ago compositions were simple. For instance, alloy technologies have evolved a lot. Before you maybe only had steel with iron and carbon, now you can have 10-15 elements inside in a very slow composition that you cannot separate (if below 0.01%), in an economically viable manner, although it would be technically possible.”

“Fifteen years ago, there were clear electronic product categories (consumer, automotive, mobile) and you could easily identify a PCB layer stack (number of layers, copper area ratio per layer). Nowadays, this is no longer true, and the variety of boards is rising. We see differences in PCB stacks from one customer to another, even in the same product category. Complexity is rising. Number of layers is always increasing, at minimum just to route ICs, even if the PCB itself is smaller.”

5. Opportunities

5.1 Reasons for adopting 6R approaches

The commitment to making products safer, more efficient, and environmentally responsible naturally extends into adopting Circular Economy principles, particularly through the implementation of 6R practices. The integration of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) into product development and service offerings has helped SME to compete in a very complex market. As one industry representative highlights,

“we might not be able to compete massively on price, so we offer a LCA service integrated in product development”

From another perspective, economic considerations heavily influence repair versus replacement decisions, especially in critical infrastructure sectors where certifying new components, such as printed circuit boards (PCBs), can incur substantial costs, often making repair the more viable option despite potential reliability trade-offs associated with modular design:

“...certifying a new PCB costs more (300k to 1 M euros per PCB) than certifying a repair...”

Sustainability is increasingly recognized as a core factor, especially because of tightening environmental regulations and growing consumer demand for greener products. Customers engaged in recycling processes show heightened sensitivity to chemical usage and emissions, motivated by environmental impact concerns and public perception. Following one of the statements collected,

“Customer are also more concerned about gas emissions... because it is something that the general population is aware of and that is not good for their image.”

Research institutions emphasize the importance of idealism and commitment to global sustainability agendas, with personal convictions motivating efforts to advance circularity and environmental impact reduction. Industry trends reveal a rising demand for remanufacturing solutions that offer cost-effective warranties and extended product lifetimes, prompting the development of improved reliability processes such as enhanced solder joint techniques. Reflecting on past practices, it was observed that

“In the past, reworking of PCBs and reuse of components was actually forbidden by certain OEMs. Now this is starting to change.”

Overall, the integration of Circular Economy strategies is becoming a strategic imperative across the electronics sector, balancing economic viability, regulatory compliance, and environmental stewardship.

5.2 Regulations to support organizations in their transition

Recent regulatory developments are steering the electronics industry towards greater sustainability. As one scientist observed,

"Regulations are moving in the right direction. They require systematic Life Cycle Assessments (LCA) of products, anticipation of critical raw materials within products, and management of toxic substances. From my perspective, these regulations are positive steps forward."

These regulations promote Circular Economy principles by encouraging product repairability. As one expert observed,

"When a company places a product on the market, it becomes responsible for its repair, creating a win-win situation if all parties communicate effectively to address repair challenges."

Similar initiatives across Europe, driven by the European Union, aim to build ecosystems where stakeholders cooperate on circularity, including trust in second-hand components. Tools like repairability indices assist consumers and supply chain actors alike, supporting transparency and sustainability in product lifecycles. However, challenges persist due to historical resistance from industry and large corporations seeking to protect market positions by influencing regulatory criteria.

Current regulations, including the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation and directives such as RoHS and WEEE, strongly support the 6R strategy by mandating eco-design and recycling objectives. These frameworks are widely viewed as opportunities rather than obstacles, driving innovation in sustainable product design and enabling companies to position themselves as leaders in environmentally responsible semiconductor development. As one interviewed noted,

"I haven't found yet any regulations that are a barrier to eco design... we need more regulations enforced to reduce the amount of material we consume."

Furthermore, stricter legislative demands in some countries and emerging European Sustainability Reporting Standards are increasing the necessity for comprehensive LCA data and digital product passports, which include CO₂ footprint disclosures.

New norms such as ISO 9001 on recyclability, ISO 14001 for environmental management, and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) requirements are becoming increasingly prevalent among clients, demanding traceability and justification for design decisions, including reliability and failure mode analyses.

"ISO 9001 recyclability, ISO 14001, CSR in client companies. We are beginning to see these requirements coming from our clients' customers. We are seeing new requirements for traceability and justification for new designs."

Safety regulations also provide strong support, with some small and medium enterprises (SMEs) achieving high standards such as "Platinum" certification and actively participating in shaping future mobility-related regulations.

While legislation is essential to initiate change, economic considerations remain critical. As one industry participant noted,

"Such changes are not very economically positive for companies. Legislation is necessary to force companies to change, at least at the beginning... then maybe they will realize that it's better for the product, it's better for the company, for the way they are perceived by customers."

In some sectors, regulatory changes are already reshaping markets. For example, legislation enabling compatibility of Wi-Fi routers across providers is reducing market fragmentation and fostering sustainability. Similarly, the End of Life Vehicle Regulation mandates separate

recycling of printed circuit boards (PCBs) larger than 10 square centimetres, significantly increasing vehicle recycling rates.

Standardization efforts are underway to support repair and refurbishment practices. Committees such as IEC TC 91, DKE TC 682-3, and IEC TC 47, often in collaboration with automotive OEMs, are developing requirements for component manufacturers and repair processes. Investment in these bodies is seen as a strategic advantage, enabling companies to anticipate customer needs and maintain competitiveness. As expressed,

“Laws drive things forward. While banning materials brings stress to manufacturers, regulation speeds evolution. Makes a lot of sense if done in a reasonable manner.”

In summary, evolving regulations and standards are pivotal drivers of the Circular Economy in electronics, fostering innovation, collaboration, and transparency while balancing economic and environmental objectives. Proactive engagement with these frameworks positions industry actors to lead in sustainable design and circular practices.

5.3 Towards new Business Models

The increasing demand for more sustainability and circularity has opened new markets and opportunities. For instance, in research, the rise of funding on environment topics has helped laboratories develop their expertise in such domains:

“The research business model is unique; we do a lot of fundraising, and I would say that funding proposals have evolved with environmental constraints. At first, our group only did circuit design until 2017-2018, then we had our first PhD student working on the subject, and now we are a team of four or five full-time staff. The business model has not changed, only the topics we are working on, or rather the markets, if I can put it that way”.

Likewise, a system manufacturer explained that including LCA in their design processes provided them with access to new markets:

“The LCA work we do represent a small percentage of what we sell, but it’s allowing us to put our product on a green marketplace. For instance, on Amazon, if you have a certified LCA of your carbon footprint, you can buy offsets, and then it becomes a green product. And theoretically, if more people buy the product on this market, we benefit as well because we are manufacturing it.”

Organizations also emphasized the creation of new partnerships around circularity indicators. Besides, circularity provides companies opportunity to develop their range of services. For instance, a system manufacturer explained:

“A new business unit is being created which is geared towards offering vehicle lifetime solutions: after-market, repair, remanufacturing, reverse logistics. This means that this has now been identified as offering business potential. We are selling repair kits to garages and performing new business case studies including redesign of products for better disassembly”.

Indeed, companies are realizing the business potential of their end-of-use products, for reuse, repair, remanufacturing, but also for recycling. As explained by a recycling company:

“The industry has been changing over the past four years, driven not only by environmental concerns but also by resilience issues. The traditional linear business model—buying scrap, extracting metals, and selling them—is evolving into a more circular approach. Increasingly, companies aim to retain ownership of their waste, positioning themselves as transformation specialists rather than simple sellers. There is growing recognition of the importance of enhancing recyclability and reusability, with a particular focus on recyclability”.

Some companies are also transitioning towards *“as-a-service models for some products, ensuring long term sustainability”*.

5.4 New Technological developments as 6R enablers

Several technologies have been identified as supporting increasing energy efficiency and decreasing energy losses. For instance, in Power Electronics, Wide Band Gap (WBG) semi-conductors (SiC & GaN) *“enable higher energy efficiency”*. For photovoltaics (PV), Active PV balancing (balance energy between battery cells to avoid dissipating energy), also helps minimize losses.

Other technologies also help reduce material consumptions. In Power Electronics, WBG also help for more compact systems. Likewise, for electronic components, *“Advanced Packaging Technologies minimize material usage and simplify recycling processes”*. An organization, also highlighted Printed Electronics really allows for less energy and material consumption than with traditional PCB, *“especially if one can move to a roll-to-roll process, it is the same as they are using in for printing newspapers. Everything is on a roll. It has a super low impact because it is basically the equivalent of mass production for printed electronics”*.

New design processes and tools are also fostering more efficient systems. For instance, Digital Twins and AI tools can *“optimize resource use during design and manufacturing phases”*.

Some technologies can help extend system use duration. For example,

“AI could help for predicting failure returns and analyzing data against qualification test benches. This would generate a lot of data to improve the rejuvenation process on functional cards without waiting for them to fail. This would allow the replacement of components identified as potentially failing ensuring continuity of operation and avoidance of machine/plant shutdowns”.

Furthermore, new analysis technologies allow qualify *“as new”*, use electronic cards.

“Is it possible to recertify cards as “like new”? This is the case for all cards in a nuclear power plant; they have all been recertified. We have the possibility to check component aging and perform an analysis of why the card is aging. We use X-ray, structural study of the card. We review the choice of components, and their values as well as the environment in which the card is used. It's amazing how far these analyses can be taken. If you ask the right questions, it's easy to create designs that stand the test of time. The quality of the components also plays a role”.

Other technologies have been identified as great way to foster circularity. Automatic or roboticized disassembly, sorting, fault detection and even repair would be a way to treat electronical waste more effectively and profitably.

“When robotics will allow automated disassembly and the sorting of components it will be very helpful. If you are a company receiving all the PCBs from different sources

and you cannot separate it by composition, then you will have a mix where it is impossible to recover anything. For now, PCB waste is just crushed, they crush it, they do not pay some humans to sort it as they cost a lot, but this way, you have a lot of contaminants and also losses of materials that you cannot recover anymore because they are all together”.

“Semi-automatic approaches are used to repair high-value boards in pre-consumer waste streams: automatic equipment is used to control heating, handling and vision system, but is still operated by a human. Currently, for lower-cost consumer products, this is done by hand in low-income countries with low worker safety laws. Automatic processes are required for better reproducibility and robotics start-ups are starting to appear to address this. I have the fantasy of automatic identification of failed components and automatic learning of repair/rework strategies of assembly”.

The Digital Product Passport could help support such automation, and for example could be *“useful in the collection phase to identify components that should be recovered for remanufacturing”.*

To improve recycling of electronics, new recycling technologies are also promising, such as:

“The use of solvo-metallurgy instead of hydro and pyro-metallurgy where mild organic compounds are used to retrieve critical materials. Still, this is not at industrial scale yet”. Likewise, “some pyrometallurgical process are evolving. For example, the TSL is a furnace that is working very well for the PCBs and recover the copper”.

Finally, specific technologies for PCBs can support more circularity.

“For example, advances in technologies such as spin-coating or circuit board design enable the integration of semiconductors in ways that facilitate easier dismantling and repair. Repairability is a key focus, as modular systems allow components to be replaced or fixed more efficiently”.

6. Conclusions

In this last section, we would like to conclude presenting the most powerful elements participants shared during the interviews, especially regarding the best course of action towards increased circularity and sustainability. We also conclude with special remarks about the role of data in promoting the transition to 6R approaches for electronics ecosystems.

6.1 Taking action

All interviewees were unanimous: the most effective way to decrease the impacts of electronics is through legislation, to provide companies with incentive to improve the design of their system (for more circularity and reduced environmental impacts), and to adapt their business model, but also to reduce the amount end-consumers are consuming.

“And then again the legislation but not in a bad way of legislation. Not legislation like punishment more educational incentives, and design (for disassembly, recycling) [...] We can design the processes, we can get very good results from the technical point of view, but at the end of the day, if the company is not implementing it, there's no point for doing it, So legislation, again, legislation, I don't feel anything else”.

“Legislation is probably the best course of action to both reduce the amount we are consuming and then to reduce the impact of what we are consuming”.

“I think a game changer would be a strict legislation on how we produce our products ensuring products can be repaired. Strict regulations are needed to force companies to repair, refurbish, otherwise, they are not going to do it”.

“EU-wide policy incentives for recyclable and repairable electronics is needed”.

“Increased customer demand and regulatory mandates for green technologies are necessary”.

“However, not all companies will be able to adapt fully. For those, government support might be necessary to enable a responsible phase-out or transformation, ensuring that employees have opportunities to move to companies that are actively embracing sustainability. This approach is not about punishing companies but about enabling a smoother transition toward a greener economy”.

“I believe regulation around the six Rs represents a major game changer. Effective regulation can simplify implementation, especially if it includes labelling or quota systems. For example, having a standardized label that reflects a product's performance across the six Rs would be a powerful tool to drive change and promote sustainability”.

As highlighted in this last quote, interviewees also strengthened that legislation needs to go hand in hand with standardization for meaningful implementation. A system manufacturer explained that they need to *“Collaborate more with standardization bodies”*. For instance, there currently is a lack of standardization for environmental assessment amongst companies.

“We need industry-level LCA standardisation groups to design something similar to PEF CR. This will avoid the effort needed to understand the methodology applied by each supplier”.

“Standardized TEA-LCA decision-making frameworks are needed”.

Others also pointed out the need for LCA database standardization in addition to methodology.

“We need a great open-source database where you can - even if you do not want to put confidential data - at least put the inventory, or the impact assessment results”.

“A common material database would be great. I guess Ecoinvent is the beginning of that, but it is not specific to electronics, we would a LCA database for the common components we use. I mean, within the EF 4.0 method - whenever that comes out - they will be making a common database, I think. At least there is already 3.1, but it's not open. I think the EF 4.0, they plan to publish openly the database of products, but I don't know how good it will be”.

Indeed, several LCA database for electronic components are available on the market but the well populated ones work as black-boxes and are expensive. In the absence of such database, tools such as IMEC's imec.net.zero are very useful.

“They [IMEC] gather data directly from their foundry. You don't have all the transparency, but they provide their methodology. You might not know the exact amount of energy, but you can see that they are doing a rigorous LCA. This is one of the ways I think we can overcome this challenge we have with the data for electronics. It uniformized as well. Everyone has the same result and we can compare it’.

Several participants mentioned the need for increased collaboration within the supply chain, between organizations of the same sectors, and with e-waste management companies to foster more circular and sustainable practices.

“Collaborate with stakeholders to improve supply chain circularity”.

“This transformation can be fostered if companies, especially those within the same industrial sector, collaborate and collectively decide to redirect their business models”.

“Establishing partnerships for robust e-waste management solutions”.

Nevertheless, such change first requires a change of mindset within companies and end-users.

“The pressing challenge today is to transform how companies address environmental and economic issues immediately, without waiting for future generations who will face even greater difficulties such as stricter pollution limits and increased emissions constraints. Changing mindsets within existing industries is crucial to make this shift happen now”.

“Educating new generations of students with fresh perspectives and skills is vital, as they may bring innovative approaches to companies resistant to change, ultimately fostering a shift in mindset and enabling progress”.

“Raising awareness of all these issues among the general public. The challenges I mentioned are the lack of data, documentation and cost-effectiveness of the 6Rs. All these points could be less of a burden if society acted in a more conscious manner”.

Research has been identified as a key enabler for improved circularity and reduced environmental impacts as they provide new processes, materials, methodologies and analyses that can be used by manufacturers and legislators.

“One should invest more in research because if you do not have the [recycling] process, you will never implement them”.

“One should invest in R&D for recyclable and biodegradable semiconductor materials”.

“To accelerate change, it is crucial to improve the ability to assess various impacts—environmental, socio-technical, and economic—through tools like impact assessments, scenario analyses, and expert studies (e.g., white papers). These assessments provide tangible data that help companies and policymakers make informed decisions on regulations, taxation, and investments to drive transformation. Addressing these challenges requires ongoing research to support the ecosystem’s capacity for assessment and action”.

“From a personal point of view, I would say we should apply our research more effectively to the economic world. We should invest more in high-impact projects. At the moment, I think we are too theoretical. We are already doing this by choosing our areas of application and focusing on topics that interest manufacturers, but we could go even further and invest in them. Ultimately, research is needed to bring about change, and to do that, I think we need to be in touch with reality in order to have the greatest possible impact”.

Participants also highlighted that organizations should focus on improving the design of their systems as well as their design process. AI was identified by a participant as a useful tool to support ecodesign.

“We need to integrate sustainability KPIs into product development workflows”.

“It is necessary to integrate TEA and environmental tools across all new electronic developments to drive upstream impact”.

“For me the design would be the first thing to do because it will solve a lot of things in the value chain afterwards. For me the design is very important, as described before. [...] Avoiding some kind of binders that cannot be removed without chemicals. Of course, soldering makes for more efficient systems than screwing, but in terms of disassembly, screwing is best. Sometimes disassembling requires special laser. Probably your phones would be a bit bigger if it had screws. That’s the problem: you cannot get the performance with the things that you need to then reuse or repair or recycle. Furthermore, now we are also using glues and binders, organic components, which are going to contaminate the process”.

“We always tend to think about recycling because we work in it, but we cannot forget that it is not only recycling but also designing new products. Recycling only will not solve any problem. You need also to change the composition of the new products to get really sustainable. By designing new product, I mean, stop changing technologies so fast, complexifying, or at least indicate how products are assembled, their compositions”.

“The adoption of AI-driven design tools could improve product lifecycle efficiency”.

In addition to improved design, interviewees stressed the need for improved recycling processes. Here again, a recycler identified AI as an interesting tool to improve material identification and sorting.

“One should work on the development of universal material recycling technologies for complex electronic components”.

“Automated recognition and desoldering could be very useful [to increased circularity]”.

“The company should invest in further development of scalable recyclable battery technologies.”

“We constantly need to adapt our recycling processes and processing parameters, investing not only in chemistry but also in accurately identifying the right materials within waste streams. The implementation of digital passports would greatly assist in this effort. Additionally, artificial intelligence can be a powerful tool for identifying metal content in waste, enabling more precise sorting and directing materials to the appropriate extraction processes”.

Finally, several partners explained that in order to bring such change, companies would probably need to invest in human resources, equipment and infrastructures.

“The organization should invest more in increase human capacity, the size for storing equipment and in medium-sized testing workshops”.

“The organization should invest in workforce training in eco-design and LCA/TEA”.

“Maybe we should invest in in European based production to have the whole process in-house. It is a big investment, but it means having more control over your materials and your supply chain. You would be able to reduce your environmental impact more. Especially now with all the taxes coming in (from the US), it is quite a topic, it might be best to produce in Europe as well”.

6.2 The role of data in promoting 6R

More data, please!

Circularity is synonymous with alternatives. Choosing between different circularity strategies is a complex task that requires considerable amounts of, often missing, data. This required data is of an interdisciplinary nature, from environmental impact of materials to processes (extraction, fabrication, logistics, circular value-chain processing, etc.). Missing data also concerns usage (usage conditions, wear, residual reliability, state of health, life-time events, etc.) and, while new sensors could theoretically help in this regard, the generated data would likely create new data ownership, management and sharing concerns. Other missing data include inexistent, lost or incomplete documentation.

While **data users** dream of open source databases, **data providers** know perfectly well that data is a treasure that is not shared readily. Hence data sharing needs to be incentivized and, even then, managed under the data provider’s close control.

Data challenges

Generating and collecting data is costly and time-consuming. Generating **high-quality, reliable** data is even more costly and time-consuming. This is due to the complexity of the supply chain and the need for preserving the confidentiality of business supplier/client relationships and IP. This is true ‘up-stream’ (i.e. before a product is put into use) but also ‘down-stream’, for example for failure data. This limits the capacity of research institutes to run R&D programs in these areas.

Assuming the above challenges are solved, **both data users and providers** then call out for more data standards, as these facilitate the sharing and reuse of data. Unfortunately, the development of data standards, including LCA data, is slow, costly and fundamentally a community effort with high free-riding potential.

Furthermore, all of this data typically lacks standardised, machine-readable representations, increasing the cost of data handling and processing.

Data opportunities

Some companies have turned the above challenges into business opportunities, supporting businesses in data collection, processing and audit. Many are exploiting the capabilities of LLM-based “data crunching”, to make better use of a company’s existing data that is often plentiful but unstructured and from disparate sources. New knowledge can be extracted more easily, to support new applications such as failure predictions or failure root cause analysis.

By providing protocols for the exchange of machine-readable, structured and interoperable data in a manner that inherently supports data sovereignty, both the digital product passport (DPP) and the industrial data spaces concepts, currently being rolled-out in Europe and beyond, will become increasingly useful both for data collection and circularity strategy assessment in the future.